

Relationship between Environmental Factors and Basic Science Content Delivery among Secondary School Students in Education District V, Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the role played by environmental factors as a predictor of effective content delivery in the Basic Science especially at the junior secondary school level. The study adopted Correlation research design. The study population comprised all Junior secondary school class two (JSSII) population during the 2023/2024 academic session, through purposive and simple sampling techniques, 30 students each was randomly selected from five identified schools to form a sample frame size of 150 students. A self-designed instrument titled, Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) containing 20 closed ended items on 4-likert scale was used to generate data. The instrument was validated by experts and a reliability index (r-value) of 0.891 was obtained using split -half reliability test which shows that the instrument is reliable for the study. Chi- square and Linear regression analysis was used to analyse the data tested at 0.05 significant level. The results of Ho1: indicated that $X^2_{cal} = 99.77$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 21.03. This shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$ which indicated that the hypothesis was rejected which implies that conducive learning environment influence the student's achievement in Basic science. And Ho2 results revealed that $X^2_{cal} = 78.30$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 5.40. Hence, this shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. The study concluded that environmental factors are good predictors that enhance effective content delivery in teaching of Basic science. It was further recommended among others that government and other related stake holders in education should renovate dilapidated buildings and prioritize investment in her educational system

Keywords: Environmental factors, Basic Science, Predictors, Effective content delivery, Physical structures

Introduction

Teachers teaching Basic Science in Junior Secondary Schools face considerable challenges in lessons preparation and Integrated Science teaching. First of all, those teachers need to understand the structure and nature of the discipline and learn unfamiliar knowledge, which is known as subject matter knowledge. Secondly, they need to transform the content knowledge into suitable activities analogies, demonstrations or simulations and adapt them to the different structure abilities to help them learn what is described by Shulman (2022) as pedagogical content knowledge. This review sets out to outline challenges faced by science teachers when teaching integrated science and explore the strategies used by teachers in dealing with such situations.

Inadequate background in the subject knowledge is one of the main factors that contributes to such challenges and will have an impact on the development of the teachers' pedagogical content knowledge as well as on the teachers' self-confidence and attitudes when teaching topics in integrated science. The teacher knowledge base strongly influences all aspects of teaching like preparation, planning and decision making regarding the choice of content to be learnt (Delphonso et al 2024).

Therefore, one can argue that one of the most important characteristics of being a good science teacher is having a very good basis of subject matter knowledge. However, research studies have attempted to find a relationship between subject matter knowledge and good teaching (Abell, 2019; Childs & MC Nicholls, 2020). Kind (2019) suggest that while a good background in subject matter knowledge is a pre-requisite for good teaching, it is not the only requirement. Exemplary science teachers, as argued by Shulman (2022) also need to develop pedagogical content knowledge which enables science teachers to blend content and pedagogy into an understanding of how particular topics, problem or issues are organized represented and adapted to the diverse interests and abilities of learners and presented for instruction (Shulman 2022). Magnolia et al (2019) described pedagogical content knowledge for science teaching as the transformation of several types of knowledge not only subject matter knowledge.

Conducive learning environment has been identified as essential for effective teaching and learning to take place. Olutola (2017) postulated that school learning environment which includes structural spaces, administrative spaces, spacers for conveniences and accessories are essential in facilitating teaching-learning process. In the opinions of Odufowokan (2011) learning environment is the quality and character of school life. It is based on pattern of school life experiences and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationship, teaching, learning and leadership practices, and organisation structures. A sustainable, positive school environment fosters upon the development and learning necessary for a productive, contributing and satisfying life in a democratic society. This climate includes norms, values and expectations that support people's feeling socially, emotionally and physical life. Amie-Ogan (2021) opined that gender consideration does not matter the provision of conducive classrooms and conducive environment influence their learning improvement. Odufowokan (2011) also emphasized that physical resources like spacious classrooms with proper ventilation, lighting and colour were significantly related to students' academic achievement. Wagithunu, Edabu and Sinan (2019) who affirmed that the provision and management of physical facilities such as libraries and lecture halls are core in attaining the educational objectives.

The school as a learning environment comprises physical, academic, social and cultural environments. The physical environment is made up of school location, physical features and structures within and outside the school. For example, a school may be located in urban or rural areas, noisy or quiet areas. Buildings, equipment and infrastructures available in their schools and its surroundings also constitute its physical environment. Egin (2023) revealed that quality of learning face facilities available within, the learning environment has positive relationship with the quality of teaching and learning activities which in turn influence students' academic performance.

Statement of the Research Problem

The performance of students especially in core subjects has not been encouraging over the years in our Junior Secondary Schools Egin (2023). This poor performance could indicate that teachers have lost their effectiveness as corroborated by Delphonso et al (2023) who opined that teaching still retains the old conservative approach of teachers acting as repertoire of knowledge and students the dormant recipients. Hence the poor performance could indicate that teachers have lost their pedagogical effectiveness. Riaz and Rizvi (2018) stressed that, it appears that the environment and general working conditions do not encourage teachers to do their jobs effectively. He further emphasized that in a classroom setting, elements of teaching-learning process include: teacher, students, content, learning process and learning situation. The learning situation or learning environment means the conditions in which learning take place. Each classroom has unique teaching - learning conditions. It appears that the environment and general working conditions do not motivate teachers do their jobs effectively (Childs & McMichill 2020). Another issue identified is the alarming rate at which students flee from the classrooms of some teachers, possibly due to poor teachers-students relationship with them (Abell, C.O. 2019). Some teachers are so hostile that students are discouraged from attending their class (Magnolia et al 2019). Some of them struggled to manage their classes (Egin 2023), while others struggled to motivate students to learn in their subject areas (Magnolia et al 2019). This could be one of the reasons why most students prefer to attend classes taught by teachers who have a positive relationship with their students.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the comparative relationship between environmental factors and Basic science content delivery among secondary school students in education district v, Lagos state, Nigeria. Therefore, the specific objectives of this research are to:

1. Determine relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content.
2. Compare the difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Research questions

In the context of the above objectives the following research questions were raised:

1. What is the relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content?
2. What are the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievements in Basic science?

Research Hypotheses

In the context of the above objectives and research questions the following research hypotheses will be tested:

1. There is no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Methodology

A correlation research design was used for this research and was carried out in education district V in Lagos State. The study population comprised all Junior secondary school class two (JSSII) during the 2023/2024 academic session, through purposive and simple sampling techniques, 30 students each was randomly selected from five identified schools to form a sample frame size of 150 students. The instrument used to collect data for the study was a structured questionnaire, a self-designed instrument titled, Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) containing 20 closed ended items on 4-likert scale was used to generate data. This instrument was divided into two sub-scales as each scale has 10 items. The instrument was validated by two experts in the department of Natural Science, Lagos State University of Education, Lagos. Through split-half, a reliability form, the sourced and a reliability index (r-value) was of 0.89 was obtained using split -half reliability test which shows that internal consistency was met the instrument is reliable for the study. Linear regression analysis was used to analyse the data tested at 0.05 significant level. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire- Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) containing 20 closed ended items on 4-likert scale was used to generate data. This instrument was divided into two sub-scales as each scale has 10 items. The data collected were analysed using Linear regression analysis and chi-square statistical tools were used to analyzed the data obtained from the respondent at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content.

Table 1: Chi-square Analysis on Conducive learning Environment and Students’ Achievement in Basic science

S/N	A	SA	D	S/D	TOTAL	Df	Sign	Cal.	Assymp. Sign
1.	35	46	10	9	100				
2.	16	20	44	20	100				
3.	35	20	40	5	100	12	0.05	99.77	0.00
4.	30	35	10	25	100				
5.	15	20	35	30	100				

The findings in this study indicated that there was no significant relationship. Hence in order to test this hypothesis, the data obtained from the Environmental Factors as Predictor of Effective Content Delivery in Basic Science Questionnaire (WFPECDBSQ) with Likert Scale was subjected to critical chi-square. Result showed that the calculated chi-square value is 99.77, while the critical chi-square value at 0.05 significant level is 21.03. This shows that the calculated X^2 value (99.77) is greater than the critical for value (21.03) that is the result is significant which implies that the hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Table 2: Chi-square analysis on mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

S/N	A	SA	D	S/D	TOTAL	Df	Sign	Cal.	Assymp. Sign
1.	35	20	45	5	100				
2.	15	25	30	30	100				
3.	50	35	10	5	100	12	0.05	78.30	0.00
4.	15	15	40	30	100				
5.	40	20	20	20	100				

Table two result showed that there is significant difference between the mean perception score of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science. it implies that the calculated chi-square value is 78.30, while the critical value at 0.05 significant level is 5.40. This shows that the calculated chi-square value (78.30) is greater than the critical t-value (5.40). Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there was no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the comparative relationship between environmental factors and Basic science content delivery among secondary school students in education district v, Lagos state, Nigeria and two hypotheses were generated and tested. Hypothesis 1 states that there was no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content and the results revealed that the hypothesis was rejected which implies that conducive learning environment influence the student's achievement in Basic science. The finding is in line with Wagithunu, Edabu and Sinan (2019) who affirmed that the provision and management of physical facilities such as libraries and lecture halls are core in attaining the educational objectives. In a related study of Bandele (2022) is in agreement with the above assertion states that learning facilities which is one of the factors lay pivotal role in the actualization of the educational goals and objectives by satisfying the physical, emotional, cultural, social, educational and psychological needs of students is as well as the general educational goals of the society.

Hypothesis 2, which state that there was no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science. Result indicated that the hypothesis was significant hence the hypothesis was rejected because the calculated value was greater than the table value. This findings is agreement with Amie-Ogan (2021) who opined that there was no significant difference between the mean opinion of male and female students on the extent provision of conducive classrooms influence their learning improvement also the results is similar with Odufowokan (2011) who unraveled that physical resources like spacious classrooms with proper ventilation, lighting and colour were significantly related to students' academic achievement. Therefore, it implies that there is significant difference between the mean perception score of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science.

Conclusion

The study investigated the comparative relationship between environmental factors and Basic science content delivery among secondary school students in education district v, Lagos state, Nigeria and two hypotheses were generated and tested.

H_{01} states that there was no significant relationship between the conducive learning environment and effective delivery of Basic science content. The outcome of the results indicated that $X^2_{cal} = 99.77$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 21.03. This shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$. The outcome of the results implies that conducive learning environment influence the student's achievement in Basic science, that is the hypothesis was rejected. H_{02} which state that there was no significant difference between the mean perception scores of male and female students regarding the factors contributing to their poor achievement in Basic science. The results indicated that $X^2_{cal} = 78.30$, while the X^2_{tab} at 0.05 significant level is 5.40. Hence, this shows that $X^2_{cal} > X^2_{tab}$. The study concluded that environmental factors are good predictors that enhance effective content delivery in teaching of Basic science. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Recommendations

It was revealed that there was significant relationship between the conducive learning and effective delivery of Basic science. It was also discovered that there is significant differences between the mean perception of male and female student

regarding the factors contributing to their achievement in Basic Science. Based on the results, findings and discussions of this study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Government should provide adequate classroom building and renovate the existing dilapidated structures in public secondary schools in order to provide effective content delivery in Basic science.
2. Bus stops in around the schools should be re-located.
3. Market places should not be around schools.
4. Selling of alcohol around schools premises should be discouraged.
5. Awareness and Education: Conduct workshop or informational sessions to raise awareness about the impact of noise on academic performance and encourage a culture of respect for noise control.
6. Teacher training programmes: Integrate information about the impact of study environment on academic performance into teacher's programme. Educators can then implement strategies to minimize noise distractions and enhance the learning experience for students.

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